

Correlations among Molecular Properties, Quantum Mechanical and Topological Quantities

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Manuscript received 15 February 1990, accepted 22 August 1990

The magnitudes of some molecular properties/quantum mechanical quantities of the members of a homologous series often show a linear dependence on some suitably chosen topological invariants or indices of the members. The molecular properties/quantum mechanical quantities, responding in this manner, are basically some additive results of two-atom contributions or mainly two bonded atom contributions. A few of such physical quantities are the binding energies (E_{bin}), total diatomic exchange-integral ($E_{\text{ex}} - \text{CNDO}$), sum of diatomic overlaps of adjacent bonded atoms ($\sum S_{\text{ab}}$) and molar diamagnetic susceptibilities (χ_m). Interestingly enough, the topological indices or invariants are also some additive features depending directly or indirectly on the connectivities of the pairs of vertices (atoms) of the molecules concerned. These graphical characteristics include branching indices (RBI), sum of positive topological eigenvalues ($Z = \sum \lambda_i$, $\lambda_i = \text{positive}$) and surprisingly, also, the number of vertices (N) in the molecular graph.

While the extrinsic explanations for all linear correlations between molecular properties/quantum mechanical quantities versus the topological features are offered, the intrinsic explanations are not always clear.

MANY molecular properties, evaluated experimentally or calculated quantum mechanically, exhibit strong correlations with some suitably chosen quantities dependent on the topology of the molecule. This is specially noticeable in cases of homologous series of compounds. In the past fifteen years, a number of papers have been published where one or another of the topological indices or invariants of homologous or isomeric molecules has served as a correlating factor in the gradation or quantification of molecular properties. These include, amongst others, the branching indices^{1,2,4} and distance matrix and path number³. The smooth variation of many molecular properties such as melting points, vapour pressures, thermodynamic properties with the branching indices of the alkanes was reported by Randic⁴.

Recently, a shift from observed properties to derived quantum mechanical quantities was made. The results of work in our laboratory on the correlation of topological branching indices and some quantum mechanical quantities, viz. binding energies, diatomic exchange integrals (CNDO) of alkanes, primary alcohols, carboxylic acids, silanes have also been reported⁵.

In the subsequent development by us, the gamut of investigated properties was extended to cover the diatomic overlaps ($\sum S_{\text{ab}}$ of bonded pair of atoms), the diamagnetic susceptibilities (χ_m) of alkanes and alcohols. On the topology side, the correlating variables considered were the Randic branching indices, sum of the positive eigenvalues of the adjacency matrices of the molecules ($Z = \sum \lambda_i$) and

the number of vertices (N) of the corresponding graphs of molecules.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows (i) the total diatomic overlaps of the adjacent bonded atoms $\sum S_{\text{ab}}$, (ii) molar diamagnetic susceptibility (χ_m) and (iii) branching indices of the molecules of three homologous series, viz. alkanes, alcohols and carboxylic acids.

The S_{ab} terms in (i) were calculated following Mulliken and coworkers¹.

TABLE I

Molecule*	$\sum S_{\text{ab}}$	χ_m (-10^6)	RBI	Z	N
Ethane	4.79	27.37	1.0	1.0	2
Propane	6.82	40.5	1.41	1.41	3
n-Butane	8.85	57.4	1.91	2.24	4
n-Pentane	10.88	63.05	2.41	2.71	5
n-Hexane	12.91	74.6	2.91	3.37	6
n-Heptane	14.94	85.24	3.41	4.03	7
n-Octane	16.97	96.63	3.91	4.56	8
Methanol	3.19	21.4	1.0	1.0	2
Ethanol	5.22	33.6	1.41	1.41	3
n-Propanol	7.25	45.18	1.91	2.24	4
n-Butanol	9.28	56.54	2.41	2.71	5
n-Pentanol	11.31	67.5	2.91	3.37	6
n-Hexanol	13.34	79.2	3.41	4.03	7
Acetic acid	4.62	31.54	1.73	1.71	4
Propionic acid	6.65	43.5	2.27	2.61	5
Butyric acid	8.68	55.1	2.77	3.06	6
n-Valeric acid	10.71	66.85	3.27	3.66	7
Caproic acid	12.74	78.55	3.77	4.37	8

*Homologous series of alkanes, alcohols and carboxylic acids.

The χ_m values were obtained from literature⁶. As to the branching index, in (iii), Randic's formulation was used and in such evaluations the oxygen atoms in alcohols and carboxylic acids were regarded as pseudocarbon atoms⁶.

In Fig. 1, A and B depict their excellent linear dependence on the branching indices. The correlation coefficients and the corresponding regression equations are presented in Table 2.

Having met with success with branching index as the correlating variable, naturally a search was made to rope in other graphical quantities. It was

quantum mechanical quantities and also of E_{bit} and E_{ex} , reported previously⁶, upon the stated graph theoretical invariants and indices.

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of sum of diatomic overlaps of adjacent bonded atoms (ΣS_{ab}) vs the branching index (Randic) of alkanes (1A_a), alcohols (1A_b) and carboxylic acids (1A_c). (B) Plots of $(-\chi_m \cdot 10^6)$ vs the branching index (Randic) of alkanes (1B_a), alcohols (1B_b) and carboxylic acids (1B_c).

found that the sum of positive eigenvalues Z (Table 1) of the topological matrices of the hydrogen suppressed graphs of alkane, alcohol and carboxylic acid molecules fulfils the expectation. All the quantum mechanical quantities/molecular properties (Table 1) turn out to be linear graphs of Z , a graphical invariant, as shown in Fig. 2. The branching indices likewise, and expectedly so, are linear functions of Z . The regression equations appear in Table 2. These sets of linear correlations are also paralleled by a third set (Fig. 3) when the data [columns (i) and (ii)] embodied in Table 1 are plotted against the third graphical index, viz. N , the number of vertices.

Looking at the data and graphs of the Tables 1 and 2 and Figs. 1-3, we are to explain the observed linear dependences of these molecular properties/

Fig. 2. (A) Plots of ΣS_{ab} vs Z of alkanes (2A_a), alcohols (2A_b) and carboxylic acids (2A_c). (B) Plots of $(-\chi_m \cdot 10^6)$ vs Z of alkanes (2B_a), alcohols (2B_b) and carboxylic acids (2B_c).

Fig. 3. (A) Plots of ΣS_{ab} vs the number of vertices of alkanes (3A_a), alcohols (3A_b) and carboxylic acids (3A_c). (B) Plots of $(-\chi_m \cdot 10^6)$ vs the number of vertices of alkanes (3B_a), alcohols (3B_b) and carboxylic acids (3B_c).

TABLE 2

Homologous series	Figure	(X)	(Y)	Correlation coefficient	Regression equation
Alkanes	2A _a	Z	ΣS_{ab}	0.997	$Y = 3.29X + 1.78$
		N	Z	0.997	$Y = 0.61X - 0.31$
		RBI	Z	0.998	$Y = 1.26X - 0.29$
	1A _a	RBI	ΣS_{ab}	1.0	$Y = 4.05X + 1.08$
		Z	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.99	$Y = 18.42X + 12.7$
		Z	$-\Delta H_f^\circ$	0.998	$Y = 8.04X + 12.66$
		Z	$-E_{ex}$	0.997	$Y = 0.94X + 0.59$
		Z	$-E_{bin}$	0.998	$Y = 19.61X + 11.51$
		N	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.993	$Y = 11.35X + 6.95$
		N	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 2.03X + 0.73$
3A _a	N	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 2.03X + 0.73$	
	RBI	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.99	$Y = 23.21X + 7.47$	
Alcohols	1A _b	Z	$-E_{bin}$	0.997	$Y = 19.75X + 3.16$
		Z	$-E_{ex}$	0.997	$Y = 0.95X + 0.195$
		RBI	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 4.16X - 0.43$
	2A _b	Z	ΣS_{ab}	0.997	$Y = 3.29X + 0.18$
		Z	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.997	$Y = 18.59X + 4.83$
	3A _b	N	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 2.03X - 0.87$
		N	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.999	$Y = 11.49X - 1.13$
	1B _b	RBI	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.999	$Y = 23.52X - 0.68$
		RBI	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 4.01X - 2.39$
	Carboxylic acids	1A _c	Z	ΣS_{ab}	0.995
Z			$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.995	$Y = 18.23X - 1.08$
2B _c		Z	$-E_{bin}$	0.994	$Y = 19.09X - 0.83$
		Z	$-E_{ex}$	0.995	$Y = 0.92X - (6.46 \times 10^{-3})$
3B _c		N	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	1.0	$Y = 11.74X - 15.32$
		N	ΣS_{ab}	0.999	$Y = 2.04X - 3.52$
		RBI	$(-\chi_m 10^6)$	0.999	$Y = 23.12X - 8.75$

In the first place it may be noted that the magnitudes of the above quantities (E_{bin} , E_{ex} , ΣS_{ab} , χ_m) are some additive values mainly composed of two-atom contributions. The topological invariants/indices (RBI, $Z = \sum \lambda_i$ for positive eigenvalues) are also some additive results depending directly (as in RBI) or indirectly (as in $\sum \lambda_i$) on the adjacent two-atom connectivities in the corresponding hydrogen suppressed graphs (HSG).

Secondly, for successive members of homologous series (SMHS), the respective quanta of increments in any of the first set of quantities (ΔE_{bin} , ΔE_{ex} , $\Delta \Sigma S_{ab}$, $\Delta \chi_m$) and in any of the second set of graphical quantities (ΔRBI , ΔZ , ΔN) happen to be two constants (or nearly so). This approximate constancy in variation can be established, as shown here² after, from an analysis of the general theoretical structures of the corresponding quantum mechanical and topological quantities. It is thus realised that the constant variations in the sets of quantities, invariants and indices are the extrinsic cause for the predicted and observed straight-line correlations of the data in Table 1 (Figs. 1-3), the consequent regression equations of Table 2 and also of the data and figures reported earlier⁵.

It now remains for us to establish the near constancy in quantum of increments of the different quantities (quantum mechanical and graphical) for successive members of a homologous series.

$$\Delta(\Sigma S_{ab}) :$$

$$\Delta(\Sigma S_{ab}) = [\langle \phi_{sp^3(C)} | \phi_{sp^3(C)} \rangle + 2\langle \phi_{sp^3(C)} | \phi_{1s(H)} \rangle]$$

from one member to the next in a homologous series

of alkanes, alcohols and carboxylic acids due to insertion of a $-\text{CH}_2-$ group. The right-hand-side of the relation at once shows that $\Delta(\Sigma S_{ab})$ is a constant for any pair of successive members.

$$\Delta E_{ex} :$$

Constancy of ΔE_{ex} for two consecutive members of a homologous series is apparent from the expression,

$$\Delta E_{ex} = \left\{ 2 \left| \begin{array}{c} A' \\ \Sigma \\ \mu' \end{array} \right| - (1/2) P_{\mu'\nu'}^2 \gamma_{A'B'} \right\} + \left\{ \begin{array}{c} AA' \\ \Sigma \Sigma \\ \mu \mu' \end{array} \right| - (1/2) P_{\mu\mu'}^2 \gamma_{AA'} \right\} + 2 \left| \begin{array}{c} A \\ \Sigma \\ \mu \end{array} \right| - (1/2) P_{\mu\nu}^2 \gamma_{AB'} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where the symbols carry the usual significances as used in the CNDO theory⁷. While A represents atoms in any member, A' stands for additional carbon atom and B' for one H-atom in each inserted CH_2 group of the next homologue; $\mu' = s, p_x, p_y$ and p_z orbitals on carbon atom and $\nu' = 1s$ orbital of the H-atom of the added CH_2 group.

Remembering that the magnitudes of the diatomic exchange terms are appreciable only for two connected atom, ΔE_{ex} (equation 1) can be approxi-

mated as

$$\Delta E_{ex} = 2 \sum_{\mu'}^{A'} - (1/2) P_{\mu'\nu'}^2 \gamma_{A'B'} + 2 \sum_{\mu}^A \sum_{\mu'}^{A'} - (1/2) P_{\mu\mu'}^2 \gamma_{AA'} \quad (2)$$

The third term of equation (1) drops out for reasons of negligible values due to non-connectivity. A major part of the second term is reasonably discarded due to their insignificant magnitudes on account of non-connectedness of the atoms concerned. Only terms involving adjacent carbon atoms on either side of the inserted $-\text{CH}_2-$ group in the new homologue are retained from the second terms of equation (1).

It is then evident that ΔE_{ex} (equation 2) remains constant for successive pairs of members of a homologous series. This is also borne out by actual computation of ΔE_{ex} by CNDO/2 technique for alkanes, alcohols and carboxylic acids⁶. The value of ΔE_{ex} for successive members is found to be -0.59 a.u. approximately (Table 3).

TABLE 3

Molecule	E_{ex} a.u. (CNDO/2)	ΔE_{ex} (a.u.) ($E_j - E_i$); $j = i + 1$
Ethane	-1.457	-0.592
Propane	-2.049	-0.585
Butane	-2.614	-0.587
Pentane	-3.201	-0.586
Hexane	-3.787	-0.587
Heptane	-4.374	-0.587
Octane	-4.961	-0.587
Methanol	-1.066	-0.585
Ethanol	-1.651	-0.587
Propanol	-2.238	-0.586
Butanol	-2.824	-0.587
Pentanol	-3.411	-0.587
Hexanol	-3.998	-0.587
Acetic acid	-1.641	-0.592
Propionic acid	-2.233	-0.594
Butyric acid	-2.827	-0.592
Valeric acid	-3.419	-0.589
Caproic acid	-4.008	-0.589

ΔE_{bin} :

The expression for binding energy⁸ is given by :

$$E_{bin} = (1/2) \left[\left\{ \sum_i \left(\frac{q_i^2}{2r_i} \right) + \sum_{j < i} \left(\frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \right) \right\} - \sum_{A < B} \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + k_n n \right) \sum_{\mu}^A \sum_{\nu}^B P_{\mu\nu}^2 \gamma_{AB} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$= (1/2) (Q + E_{ex} + k_n n E_{ex}) \text{ a.u.} \quad (4)$$

where, Q is the electrostatic work done in constructing an assembly of charges, E_{ex} the diatomic electron-exchange energy, n the number of valence orbitals and k_n a proportionality constant.

The electrostatic part, Q of equation (3) is extremely small compared to the second part involving the exchange energy (Table 3). Binding energy is, therefore, determined by E_{ex} . The constancy of ΔE_{ex} for successive members (equation 2) ensures the constancy of ΔE_{bin} in a homologous series.

$\Delta \chi_m$:

Pascal's empirical relation⁹ and Pople's GIAO based molecular orbital approach¹⁰ show that molar diamagnetic susceptibility is mainly a sum of atomic contributions. Expressed in terms of constituent atomic diamagnetic susceptibilities, the semiclassical expression for χ_m of a substance having molecular formula $A_j B_k C_l$ is :

$$\chi_m = - \left(\frac{Ne^2}{6mc^2} \right) \left\{ j \sum_{\mu} \overline{r_{\mu}^2} + k \sum_{\nu} \overline{r_{\nu}^2} + l \sum_{\eta} \overline{r_{\eta}^2} \right\}$$

where $\overline{r_{\mu}^2}$ is the mean square distance of an electron present in a single-electron orbital of atom A and summation covers all such different single-electron orbitals of A , N is the Avogadro number and e and m are electronic charge and mass respectively.

Since most molecules in the ground states have zero spin ruling out paramagnetic contribution and orbitally the electrons are also paired, these single-electron contributions of the atoms may be appropriately paired (pairs of inner shell electrons and pairs of bonded electrons in the overlaps of the valence orbitals of the two atoms) to enable χ_m to be expressed as a sum of two-electron contribution units, d_i 's and d_v 's, the inner shell pair contribution and valence bond pair contribution respectively. $\chi_m = N(\sum_i d_i + \sum_v d_v)$ for all electron pairs in a gram mole of a substance.

It is, therefore, evident that $\Delta \chi_m$ for SMHS is just a net sum of N times two d_i 's and three (not four) individual d_v 's due to the entry of a $-\text{CH}_2-$ group in the higher of the two homologues. Thus $\Delta \chi_m$ remains a constant for SMHS.

ΔRBI :

$$RBI = \sum_{i < j} (v_i v_j)^{-1/2}$$

where v_i and v_j are the degrees of the vertices (carbon atoms) in the hydrogen suppressed graph of the molecule.

The incorporation of a $-\text{CH}_2-$ group in passing from one member to the next in a homologous series amounts to an increment of a vertex of degree 2. This adds a contribution of ≈ 0.5 to the RBI of the new homologue over and above the RBI of the preceding one. ΔRBI , consequently, remains constant in a homologous series of alkanes, alcohols and carboxylic acids.

ΔZ :

It is considered that for each $(n \times n)$ order topological matrix, an auxiliary $(n \times n)$ order matrix which is a direct sum of a $[(n-2) \times (n-2)]$ order and a (2×2) order matrices constructed from the original matrix by replacing the $(n-2)(n-1)$ th and the $(n-1)(n-2)$ th off-diagonal matrix elements by zeros. Both the original matrix and the auxiliary direct sum matrix will yield n number of eigenvalues each. But in general,

$$\sum_i \lambda_{i(n)}^R \approx \sum_i \lambda_{i(n-2)}^A + \sum_i \lambda_{i(2)}^A$$

for the positive eigenvalues where the superscripts R and A represents the real and the components of the auxiliary matrices respectively. However, for any two SMHS we can assume, for positive eigenvalues, that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Z &= \sum_i \lambda_{i(n+1)}^R - \sum_i \lambda_{i(n)}^R \\ &\approx \left[\sum_i \lambda_{i(n+1-2)}^A + \sum_i \lambda_{i(2)}^A - \sum_i \lambda_{i(n-2)}^A - \sum_i \lambda_{i(2)}^A \right] \end{aligned}$$

for $(n+1)$ -vertex and n -vertex HSG's of the molecules. This assumption of near equality is based upon the fact that both the auxiliary direct sum matrices are built up in exactly the same way by changing the corresponding pair of off-diagonal matrix elements from 1 to 0 of the actual topological matrices of $[(n+1) \times (n+1)]$ and $(n \times n)$ orders.

The evaluations of $\sum_i \lambda_i$ for positive eigenvalues of all such direct sum matrices can be made consecutively once the actual solutions of a (2×2) and of a (3×3) order topological matrices are worked out initially. A set of such calculations are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4— ΔZ FOR POSITIVE EIGENVALUES

Order of topological matrices	$\sum_i \lambda_i$ (positive eigenvalues)	ΔZ (SHMS)
(2×2)	X (1.0)	
(3×3)	Y (1.414)	$(Y - X) = 0.414$
(4×4)	2X	$(2X - Y) = 0.586$
(5×5)	Y + X	$(Y - X) = 0.414$
(6×6)	3X	$(2X - Y) = 0.586$
(7×7)	Y + 2X	$(Y - X) = 0.414$
(8×8)	4X	$(2X - Y) = 0.586$
(9×9)	Y + 3X	$(Y - X) = 0.414$
(10×10)	5X	$(2X - Y) = 0.586$

It thus transpires that a pair of recurrence relations give for SMHS values of ΔZ alternating between two close values, viz. 0.414 and 0.586. This approximates to a constant average of 0.5 for the consecutive members of the entire homologous series.

ΔN :

ΔN for the consecutive members of a homologous series is always unity. Properties, both quantum mechanical/molecular, that vary regularly in a homologous series should, therefore, exhibit linear correlations with the number of vertices in the graphs.

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